

OSPARK Research Protocol Appendix 5: Study 2 Survey

Notes:

- *This survey is adapted from a pilot survey conducted by [Iley, Abdelkader, et al. \(2025\)](#).*
- *The participant information sheet, consent form, and closing message are adapted from [templates](#) provided by the Research Governance Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.*
- *Each level 1 heading represents a new page in the online survey.*

Page 1: Participant information sheet and consent form

Title of study: Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Study 2: Survey of needs and barriers.

Thank you for your interest in taking part in this study. Before you decide whether to participate, it is important that you understand why this research is being conducted and what it will involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully. You may discuss it with others if needed.

Please contact us if you have any questions or need further information. Our contact details are further down the page.

This content is adapted with permission from [participant information sheet and consent form templates](#) developed by the Research Governance, Ethics and Integrity Team at Queen's University Belfast.

Quick summary

- This study is being organised by researchers from OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH).
- We are aiming to identify the outreach, marketing, and communications activities that open science advocates take part in; the barriers they experience regarding these activities; and their needs and preferences regarding training in these topics. We

would also like to assess how knowledgeable and confident open science advocates are about core concepts in outreach activities.

- As part of this study, you will be asked to take part in a survey. This will involve both open and closed questions. We expect that this will take most people 15-20 minutes to complete.
- Your data will be stored on the survey platform and will be accessible only to the [OLS](#) and [DRA](#) teams until data analysis begins. Anonymous data will be shared on an openly accessible GitHub and/or Zenodo repository. All data storage will be in compliance with UK data protection legislation.
- This study is part of the Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK) Bootcamp, funded by the first OSCARS Open Call. The OSCARS project has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to understand how open science advocates engage in outreach activities, and what barriers prevent them from doing so. It also aims to identify what training open science advocates feel they need in marketing, communications, and outreach activities. We would also like to assess how knowledgeable and confident open science advocates are about core concepts in outreach activities.

Who can take part?

We are seeking responses from anyone who is involved in an open science initiative, project, service, or infrastructure. We expect this will mainly be researchers, research professionals, or students who are engaged in open science. We are aiming to recruit at least 77 people to participate in this study.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study will involve taking a survey about outreach, marketing, and communications in open science. This will involve:

1. Giving informed consent;
2. Providing information about your existing outreach activities;
3. Responding to questions about the barriers to conducting such activities that you have experienced;
4. Answering knowledge-based questions about outreach, marketing, and communications;
5. Giving some information about your confidence conducting outreach activities;
6. Providing some demographic information;

7. Closing message.

We expect that this will take most people 15-20 minutes to complete.

What will happen to my data?

This research will be conducted in compliance with data protection legislation. Your data will be stored and managed by OLS (Open Life Science Limited), a UK based social enterprise. As part of this study, we will be collecting your anonymous survey responses. No identifiable data (such as IP addresses) will be collected.

This study has been designed according to open science principles. Anonymised data will therefore be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International \(CC-BY\)](#) license, unless deemed to be a risk to participant safety or wellbeing.

Our full data management plan [<add link when available>](#) is publicly accessible.

What are the possible benefits, risks, or disadvantages of taking part?

The benefit of taking part in this study is having the opportunity to shape training on outreach, marketing, and communications for open science initiatives.

There is a risk that your responses may be identifiable, despite anonymity, as there are some open text boxes. To mitigate this, the researchers will check open text responses and anonymise any potentially identifiable information.

What if something goes wrong?

If you have any concerns about any aspects of the study, you should contact the lead researcher:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

Should you remain unhappy with the response and wish to make a formal complaint, please make a report under OLS's [Code of Conduct policy](#).

What will happen to the results of the research?

Upon conclusion of this study, the findings may be written into a scientific journal article and presented at scientific conferences. This is to share our results with other researchers in the

field. You can get updated about the findings of this research by signing up to the [OSPARK mailing list](#).

The anonymous data from this study will be shared publicly under a [Creative Commons Attribution \(CC-BY\) 4.0 International license](#). This means that other researchers may use the data to verify our results or conduct their own research in the future.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This study is led by a team of researchers at OLS (Open Life Science Limited) and DRA (DRA Digital Research Academy GmbH). OLS is a non-profit company limited by guarantee, based in the United Kingdom (company number [12824090](#)). DRA is a grassroots trainer network based in Germany (HRB 295646).

The research team for this study consists of the following people:

- Bethan Iley, OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager, OLS
- Heidi Seibold, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Joyce Kao, Co-Executive Director, DRA
- Yo Yehudi, Co-Executive Director, OLS

The development of this survey was also supported by contributions from the following individuals:

- Doaa Abdelkader, The British University in Egypt & Open Science Community Egypt, Egypt.
- Anastasiia Afanaseva, Saarland University, Germany
- José Francisco Pereira Cardoso, Department of Clinical Sciences, University of Lund, Sweden.
- Jens Dierkes, University and City Library Cologne, University of Cologne, Germany.
- Christian Meesters, NHR SouthWest, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz, Germany.

The development of the overall research project was additionally supported by the following people:

- Deborah Udoh, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Nigeria
- Riva Quiroga, Open Life Science Ltd, United Kingdom/Chile

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Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed by *<name of research ethics committee or IRB>*. If you have any questions or concerns about the ethics review for this study, you can contact them at *<IRB email>* using reference *<reference number>*.

Contact for Further Information

If you have questions or comments about the study, please contact the lead researcher on this study:

Bethan Iley
OSPARK Coordinator & Finance Manager
bethan@we-are-ols.org

If your questions or concerns remain unresolved, please contact the Principle Investigator:

Yo Yehudi
Executive Director
yo@we-are-ols.org

Thank you for your interest in this study and for taking the time to read through this information page.

Please indicate you understand and consent to taking part in this research using the checkboxes below.

- I confirm that I have read, or had read to me, and understand the information presented above about this study. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and these have been answered fully.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving any reason and without my legal rights being affected.
- I understand the study is being conducted by researchers from Open Life Science Limited and that my personal information will be held and handled in compliance with data protection legislation.
- I understand that data collected as part of this will be accessible to employees and contractors at Open Life Science Limited (also known as OLS) and DRA Digital

Research Academy GmbH (also known as DRA). I give permission for these individuals to have access to this information.

- I understand that the information I provide may be published as a report. Anonymity will be maintained and it will not be possible to identify me from any publications.
- I agree that my anonymous survey responses can be deposited in repositories such as GitHub and/or Zenodo to promote transparency and public accessibility to research.
- I agree to take part in the above study.

Page 2: Outreach activities

We are defining outreach activities as anything which **reaches out to and/or engages the community around your open science initiative**. This could include a range of marketing and communications activities, such as managing social media accounts, newsletters, or events.

What outreach activities are you currently engaged in for the open science initiative(s) you are part of?

- Creating social media posts
- Managing email lists or sending newsletters
- Blogging
- Academic writing, such as preprints or journal articles
- Hosting events (e.g. hackathons, conference sessions)
- Collecting feedback, such as user research
- Creating podcasts
- Creating video content, such as vlogs or TikToks
- Community building activities
- Other (please specify): _____

Which outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of would you like to try in the future?

- Creating social media posts
- Managing email lists or sending newsletters
- Blogging
- Academic writing, such as preprints or journal articles

- Hosting events (e.g. hackathons, conference sessions)
- Collecting feedback, such as user research
- Creating podcasts
- Creating video content, such as vlogs or TikToks
- Community building activities
- Other (please specify): _____
- None of the above

Page 3: Barriers

What stops you from engaging in outreach activities for your open science initiative(s)?

Knowledge and skills

- I don't know how to create useful or effective outreach resources
- I lack the necessary skills, such as graphic design
- I'm not confident that I can represent the initiative correctly
- I'm not sure which channels to use (for example, which social media platforms to post on)

Prioritisation and resources

- I don't have enough time to do outreach activities
- I don't enjoy doing outreach activities
- My community don't have enough time to engage in my outreach
- I do not have enough resources for outreach activities
- Outreach activities are not prioritised within my initiative
- My initiative doesn't feel like a finished product that can be shared

Community and environment

- It feels like we're competing with other initiatives
- I'm not sure who to ask for help
- Lack of interest from the community
- There is too much content and I can't break through the noise

Something else (please specify): _____

Page 4: Knowledge

The OSPARK-aligned answer is highlighted in light green.

Below is a series of 9 questions about outreach strategy. These questions will assess whether your approach aligns with OSPARK's course content. Remember that there is no "right" answer with social media strategy—every person and initiative needs a tailored approach.

Who might be in the target market for an open science initiative?

- Students
- Researchers in academia
- Researchers in industry, the public sector, or nonprofit organisations
- Research professionals and support staff, such as lab managers and librarians
- Research funders and philanthropists
- University administrators
- All of the above
- I'm not sure

Conference talks and networking sessions are a form of marketing for your open science initiative.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Which communications channel should you use to advertise your open science initiative?

- The ones with the most overall users
- The ones frequently used by the people I want to reach
- The ones which are easily accessible through my job
- I'm not sure

What is the most effective strategy to grow your open science initiative's social media page?

- Occasionally commenting on and sharing other initiatives' work
- Spending 1 hour per day "liking" every post on the account's timeline
- Using 20+ hashtags in every post, on every platform

I'm not sure

What is most important in a talk about your open science initiative?

- Providing clear information about the initiative
- Connecting emotionally with the audience
- Both are equally important
- I'm not sure

What is the main benefit of short vertical videos, such as TikToks or YouTube Shorts, over long-form videos?

- There is often better discoverability through wider algorithmic reach
- Viewers are more likely to look at your profile and other content
- It's easier to establish a connection with the audience
- I'm not sure

Marketing and communications are primarily about...

- Promoting your open science initiative
- Providing value to your audience
- I'm not sure

Interacting with similar or competing open science initiatives is harmful to your open science initiative's marketing and communications goals.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

What would normally be included in a marketing and communications strategy plan?

- Broad guidance about the goals, style, tone, and channels you will use
- Specific step-by-step instructions on how to create each social media post
- I'm not sure

This is an attention check. Please select "false" to show that you are paying attention.

- True
- False
- I'm not sure

Page 5: Self-efficacy

Imagine you were asked to conduct outreach activities for the open science initiative(s) you are part of. How confident would you feel doing this?

1. Not at all confident
- 2.
- 3.
- 4.
5. Very confident

Please think about conducting outreach activities for an open science initiative. When you think about these activities, to what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

Note: Rated on a 5-point Likert scale: strongly disagree (1), slightly disagree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), slightly agree (4), strongly agree (5).

- I will be able to achieve most of the goals that I have set for myself.
- When facing difficult tasks, I am certain that I will accomplish them.
- In general, I think that I can obtain outcomes that are important to me.
- I believe I can succeed at most any endeavor to which I set my mind.
- I will be able to successfully overcome many challenges.
- I am confident that I can perform effectively on many different tasks.
- Compared to other people, I can do most tasks very well.
- Even when things are tough, I can perform quite well.
- This is an attention check. Please choose "slightly agree" to show that you are paying attention.

Page 6: Training needs

What resources have you seen (online or offline) about promotion, outreach, marketing, and communications for open science?

If you were to join a training programme about outreach activities for open science initiatives, what skills or knowledge would you most like to develop?

If you were to join a training programme about outreach activities for open science initiatives, how would you prefer the training to be delivered? Choose all that apply.

- Online
- In-person
- Hybrid (online and in-person components)

Why did you choose this format (or these formats)?

Page 7: Demographics

Approximately how many years of experience do you have in research and/or research support roles? Please include any research student roles.

Please estimate how long you have been involved in open science. Please answer in years; enter "1" if it is between 1-12 months.

How would you describe your career stage?

- Exploration (student)
- Establishment (junior role, e.g. postdoctoral researcher)
- Mid-career (a role which involves managing or mentoring more junior colleagues, e.g. senior lecturer/associate professor)
- Late-career (a senior role, e.g. professor)
- Retired

Which region are you resident in?

- Africa
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Europe
- Latin America or the Caribbean
- Oceania

USA or Canada

Which region(s) did you reside in before the age of 18?

- Africa
- Antarctica
- Asia
- Europe
- Latin America or the Caribbean
- Oceania
- USA or Canada

What species are you? This is an attention check. To show that you are paying attention, please type "cat" in the box below.

Which of the following platforms do you use to find out more about open science?

- Academic writing (preprints, journal articles)
- Blogs
- Bluesky
- Events (such as conferences, hackathons)
- LinkedIn
- Mailing lists
- Mastodon
- Podcasts
- Repositories (such as Zenodo)
- X (formerly Twitter)
- Video platforms (such as YouTube or TikTok)
- Websites (such as those belonging to initiatives or universities)
- Word of mouth
- Other (please specify): _____

Page 8: Closing message

This will be shown as a post-submission message.

Title of study: Open Science Promotion and Advocacy for Research Knowledge (OSPARK)

Study 2: Survey of needs and barriers.

Thank you for your time and for taking part in this study. Below is the information from the participant information sheet. If you may need it, please save this for future reference.

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7. Reading a closing message..

We expect that this took most respondents approximately 15-20 minutes.

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